

EU projects on Time and Frequency Dissemination

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Below is a list of references and links for projects on Time and Frequency distribution, created 2023-02-20 to support the PRT submission on “Robust Time and Synchronization as European critical infrastructure”.

1. NEAT-FT, "Accurate time/frequency comparison and dissemination through optical telecommunication networks", https://www.ptb.de/emrp/neatft_home.html
2. TIMEFUNC, "Time synchronisation impact enabling future network communication", https://www.euramet.org/research-innovation/search-research-projects/details/project/time-synchronisation-impact-enabling-future-network-communication/?L=0&tx_euramettcp_project%5Baction%5D=show&tx_euramettcp_project%5Bcontroller%5D=Project&cHash=c5b02a3d44ac99d07d9cfa1844daca6a
3. WRITE, "White Rabbit for Industrial Timing Enhancement", <http://empir.npl.co.uk/write/>
4. ASTERICS, "Astronomy ESFRI and Research Infrastructure Cluster", <https://www.asterics2020.eu/>
5. CLONETS, "CLOCK NETWORK Services, Strategy and innovation for clock services over optical-fibre networks", <http://www.clonets.eu/>
6. TiFOON, "Time and Frequency Over Optical Networks"
<http://empir.npl.co.uk/tifoon/project/>